

Competency and Strategy Formulation in Automobile Industry

Chandan Deep Singh

Abstract—In present days, companies are facing the rapid competition in terms of customer requirements to be satisfied, new technologies to be integrated into future products, new safety regulations to be followed, new computer-based tools to be introduced into design activities that becomes more scientific. In today's highly competitive market, survival focuses on various factors such as quality, innovation, adherence to standards, and rapid response as the basis for competitive advantage. For competitive advantage, companies have to produce various competencies: for improving the capability of suppliers and for strengthening the process of integrating technology. For more competitiveness, organizations should operate in a strategy driven way and have a strategic architecture for developing core competencies. Traditional ways to take such experience and develop competencies tend to take a lot of time and they are expensive. A new learning environment, which is built around a gaming engine, supports the development of competences in specific subject areas. Technology competencies have a significant role in firm innovation and competitiveness; they interact with the competitive environment. Technological competencies vary according to the type of competitive environment, thus enhancing firm innovativeness. Technological competency is gained through extensive experimentation and learning in its research, development and employment in manufacturing. This is a review paper based on competency and strategic success of automobile industry. The aim here is to study strategy formulation and competency tools in the industry. This work is a review of literature related to competency and strategy in automobile industry. This study involves review of 34 papers related to competency and strategy.

Keywords—Competency, competitiveness, manufacturing competency, strategic formulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

COMPETENCIES assume a vital part in small, medium- and large scale Indian associations under different weights and requirements. SMEs ought to be as proactive as extensive associations in rolling out improvements as far as different procedures, for example, development of competencies, human resources, upgrading of technology and awareness about market changes. This will help organizations in forming their focused methods for creating skills according to the business sector needs [32].

Competencies of individual pioneers are connected to business profitability and the competencies are diversely substantial. Introductory competency examination utilizing experimental techniques ought to be utilized to help center competency models utilized for determination, input,

preparing, and execution administration [14].

Competencies refer to skills or knowledge that lead to improved performance. Competencies are formed through an individual's knowledge, abilities and skills. These divergent perspectives suggest an alternative approach that would apply multiple theories to analysis competitiveness [29], [10].

Manufacturing competency is a situation for enhanced aggressiveness. More experienced and all the more broadly prepared people or groups show improvement over less experienced or less prepared ones [11]. Capabilities in associations could be comprehensively named representative level and authoritative level [2]. Competence is a nature of individuals and associations [12].

II. REVIEW

Technology competencies assume a significant role in firm advancement and intensity, what and how technology competencies associated with focused environment influence firm development has not been completely caught on. Additionally, distinctive sorts of competitive environment oblige diverse sorts of innovative skills to improve firm inventiveness [8].

Technological competencies are multi-field, highly stable and differentiated. The manufacturing function can be a formidable weapon to achieve competitive superiority. With the increasingly turbulent and dynamic nature of competition, there is a great tendency for understanding firms in terms of the use of unique capability that creates sustained performance within industries. Companies that do not have quality competence simply will not survive and they increase their sustained competitive advantage in the global marketplace [29], [23].

ITC (Information Technology Competency) assumes a basic part in interior and outer learning capabilities. Likewise, inner and outside learning skills are straightforwardly identified with the Commercial Success of Innovation (CSI). Also, inner and outer learning capabilities intervene the connection in the middle of ITC and the CSI [7].

Innovative competency can make and utilize a specific field of innovation adequately for businesses. The contextual analysis of Escorts gives the perspective of competency so that competency improvement is a basic device to improve the aggressiveness of businesses [21].

In the strategic management literature, there is an expansive concession to the distinction between corporate strategy, business strategy, and operations strategy. These can be considered as a chain of command. Corporate strategy is conceived by extensive firms so as to give a general

arrangement to the firm [9].

Survival and success in present turbulent times progressively relies on intensity. Intensity gets through an incorporated exertion crosswise over distinctive capacities and arrangement of cutting edge producing innovations. Advanced Manufacturing Technology (AMT) assumes a noteworthy part in quality and adaptability changes in assembling associations. AMT gives advantages and points of interest in regions that would empower producers to look after quality, operational, hierarchical, and monetary exhibitions to enhance innovative aggressiveness [4].

Strategic thinking model comprises of calculated thinking capacity, visionary considering, systematic deduction capacity, blending capacity, objectivity, imagination, and learning capacity. This arrangement of capacities and talented are termed "strategic thinking competency". The "strategic thinking competency" model offers a structure for creating vital considering business pioneers and administrators which adds to better technique and better business execution. Human resource developers may apply the model for planning preparing projects to grow better vital masterminds [13].

Managerial cognition and additionally individual and corporate qualities can have an effect on key choice making. Vital abilities are critical albeit there is no concession to what those skills are. The present study checked on both mental and administration writing to give a comprehension of the vital intuition and choice making process and components that may influence the procedure [33].

Quality administration influences the vital status of value as a wellspring of maintained game changer. Quality competency assumes an essential part in maintaining leeway over the outside contenders [34].

While distinctive organizations can have solid linkage in the middle of technology and business strategy, the methodology has been sensibly diverse for acquisition of technology and its development. The discoveries propose that a successful Strategic Technology Management (STM) can add to quicker innovation retention and general business execution [15].

Competence management incorporates the administration, building, utilizing and organization of key and operational capabilities, the causal connections and linkages in the middle of them, and the way abilities are installed in hierarchical and individual assets. The vital capabilities and worldwide skills of administrators assume a huge part in firms' level of worldwide execution and innovation improvement. These skills support compelling methods to enhance the intensity of Thai organizations on a worldwide level [3].

A conceptual model has been utilized as a part of request to evaluate the effect of competencies framework. Different information investigation methods were connected to test the theory, for example, spellbinding measurements, basic relapses, and various relapses. Through the information accumulated and the speculation directed it demonstrated that there is a critical effect of the practical abilities on the firm execution, additionally generation capabilities, innovative work skills, and promoting capabilities are key determinants of proficiency and consumer loyalty [24], [25].

Core competencies and the systems that exploit them are in view of the reason that they are immaterial and uncommon. How competency, including resource based perspective ideas can fit into and help the vital standpoint they could call their own associations [27].

Organizations appear to be hesitant to receive methodologies obliging either considerable speculations or significant association rebuilding [17], [18].

Manufacturing Excellence intends to be the best in the field of aggressive need and to show industry best performs. Throughout the years, there have been numerous spearheading endeavors toward the appraisal and usage of assembling greatness through different structures; however none of the current systems was discovered to be suitable for the Indian situation, and the culmination of existing Indian fabricating magnificence systems was additionally discovered to be missing [16].

Quality and business excellence grants that perceive amazing authoritative execution have turned into a noteworthy main thrust in upgrading the aggressiveness of Indian firms in the worldwide economy. While the systems hidden these honors have been utilized widely by associations, minimal experimental confirmation exists with respect to the legitimacy of these structures as an indicator of building aggressiveness [6].

The transient competitive advantages are those which would last through a business cycle and long haul game changers are those which would last over more than one business cycle. The discernible competitive advantage which had the capability of being over the whole length of the anticipated future, then one could stamp as an "unthreatened competitive advantage [19], [20].

Manufacturing abilities impact the viability of customer coordination through this study, the idea of absorptive capacity has been given that will be connected to clear the perspective that the manufacturing capabilities are strongly associated with operational performance, and the association is the strongest for firms whose main competitive priority is operational performance. The findings suggest that assembling capacities may well appear to be nonessential, yet just on the off chance that they are surveyed in separation and when assessing them by their immediate commitment to firm execution [26], [30].

Functional strategies of market orientation, human resource management, and manufacturing have impact on competitive strategy and even performance differently between family and non-family firms. There are a few huge connections between the useful methods and aggressive system. An HR interest procedure, adaptability and a conveyance method has a critical effect on productivity for family firms yet not for non-family firms; but rather Cost fabricating technique and business introduction is identified with expense initiative system for both family and non-family firms [28].

The auto component segment is adaptable in creating techniques and those systems identifying with expense, quality; venture and competency advancement are fundamentally connected with aggressiveness. Aggressiveness

of Indian auto part segment, inside of a globalized economy with its chaperon weights and imperatives is examined. It looks at the systems received for quality change, cost lessening, speculation and competency advancement. It intends to build up the relationship in the middle of methodologies and the diverse measurements of intensity, developing strong environment, raising trusts from the business and a lack of specialized labor are obliging elements although expense, quality, and conveyance time are the principle weights on the auto part area. Associations ought to make the vital venture to grow new skills, and ought to address cost lessening and quality change [31].

To be more competitive, they have to work all the more in a technique driven manner and build up a key strategic architecture to empower their association to add to the important center capabilities. Manufacturing Strategy adds to organization level aggressiveness. Naturally, it appears glaringly evident that an easily running generation framework will have a positive impact on business execution [5].

The business based productivity assessment furnishes administration with data with regards to the moderately best practice areas in the perception sets and finds the generally wasteful parts by contrasting and the best honed ones. In light of the past writing, this study brings later points of view, for example, service exercises and monetary power to the four primary aggressive needs of expense, quality, adaptability and conveyance [1].

REFERENCES

- [1] Bulak, Muhammet Enis; Turkyilmaz, Ali; (2014) "Performance assessment of manufacturing SMEs: a frontier approach", *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol. 114 Iss: 5, pp.797 – 816
- [2] Cardy, R. L., & Selvarajan, T. T. (2006). *Competencies: Alternative frameworks for competitive advantage*. Business Horizons.
- [3] Chairasit, Sasiprapa & Swierczek, Fredric William (2011), "Competitiveness, Globalization and technology development in Thai firms", *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*, Vol. 21 No. 2, pp. 18
- [4] Dangayach G.S., Pathak S.C., and Sharma A.D. (2006), 'Advanced Manufacturing Technology: A Way of Improving Technological Competitiveness', *International Journal of Global Business and Competitiveness*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 1-8
- [5] Demeter, Krisztina (2002) 'Manufacturing strategy and competitiveness (International Journal of Production Economics', Elsevier Science B.V, pp. 205–213.
- [6] Dutta, Sanjib K. (2007) 'Enhancing competitiveness of India Inc. International Journal of Social Economics', Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Vol. 34 No. 9, pp 679-711.
- [7] Fernández-Mesa, Anabel; Ferreras-Méndez, José Luis; Alegre, Joaquin; Chiva, Ricardo; (2014) "IT competency and the commercial success of innovation", *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol. 114 Iss: 4, pp. 550 – 567
- [8] Hunag, Kuo-Feng (2011), *Technological Competencies in Competitive Environment*, *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 64, Issue 2, Page 172-179
- [9] Jones, Peter; and Parker, Alan; (2004): *Strategy execution and implementation— achieving strategic goals through operations*. Vol 42. pp.341-348.
- [10] Khamba, JS; Singh, CD and Singh H (2013), "Exploring Manufacturing Competencies of Car Manufacturing Unit", *International Conference on Advancements and Futuristic Trends in Mechanical and Materials Engineering*, (October 3-6, 2013), pp: 88-97.
- [11] Levinthal, D.A. and March, J.G. (1993). 'The myopia of learning', *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 14, No. S2 (Special No.: Organizations, Decision Making and Strategy), pp. 95-112.
- [12] Nicolini, C. (1983), 'The Power of Competency in Industrial Development', *Technology in Society*, Vol. 5, No. 3-4, pp. 167-170
- [13] Nuntamanop, Polboon; Kauranen, Ilkka & Igel, Barbara (2013), "A new model of strategic thinking competency", *Journal of Strategy and Management*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 242-264
- [14] Ryan, Geoff; Spencer, Lyle M. & Bernhard, Urs (2012), "Development and validation of a customized competency-based questionnaire Linking social, emotional, and cognitive competencies to business unit profitability", *Cross Cultural Management*, Vol. 19 No. 1, pp. 90-103
- [15] Sahoo, Tapan; Banwet, D. K. & Momaya, K. (2011), "Strategic technology management in the auto component industry in India A case study of select organizations", *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, Vol. 8 No. 1, pp. 9-29
- [16] Sharma, Monica; and Kodali, Rambabu; (2008) 'Development of a framework for manufacturing excellence', *Measuring Business Excellence*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, vol 12 no. 4, pp 50-66.
- [17] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2014), "Analysis of Manufacturing Competency for an Automobile Manufacturing Unit", *International Journal of Engineering, Business and Enterprise Applications*, Vol. 9, Issue 1, June-August 2014, pp: 44-51.
- [18] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2014), "Analysis of Strategic Success for an Automobile Manufacturing Unit", *International Journal of Engineering, Business and Enterprise Applications*, Vol. 9, Issue 2, June-August 2014, pp: 104-111.
- [19] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2014), "Evaluation of Manufacturing Competency factors on performance of an Automobile Manufacturing Unit", *International Journal for Multi-Disciplinary Engineering and Business Management*, Volume-2, Issue-2, June-2014, pp: 4-16.
- [20] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2014), "Evaluation of Strategic Success factors on performance of an Automobile Manufacturing Unit", *International Journal of Engineering Research & Management Technology*, Volume-1, Issue-4, July-2014, pp: 144-157.
- [21] Singh, CD; Khamba, JS; Singh S, and Singh N (2014), "Exploring Manufacturing Competencies of a Tractor Manufacturing Unit", *International Journal of Applied Studies*, Volume: 1, Issue: 1, Jan 2014, pp: 53-62.
- [22] Singh, CD; Singh, P; and Khamba, JS (2014), "To study the role of manufacturing competency in the performance of Preet Tractor Manufacturing Unit", *International Journal for Multi-Disciplinary Engineering and Business Management*, Volume-2, Issue-2, June-2014, pp: 4-7
- [23] Singh, CD; Singh, P; and Khamba, JS (2014), "To study the role of manufacturing competency in the performance of Sonalika Tractor Manufacturing Unit", *International Journal of Engineering, Business and Enterprise Applications*, Vol. 8, Issue 1, March-May., 2014, pp. 62-66
- [24] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2015), "Competency Strategy Model Analysis using SEM", *International Journal for Multi-Disciplinary Engineering and Business Management*, Volume-3, Issue-3, July-2015, pp: 37-41.
- [25] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2015), "AHP Analysis of Manufacturing Competency and Strategic Success Factors", *International Journal in Applied Studies and Production Management*, Volume-1, Issue-2, May-August 2015, pp: 357-373.
- [26] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2015), "Manufacturing Competency & Economic Effects: A Review", *Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering, Science and Technology*, Vol. 3, No. 2, September 2015, pp: 16-20
- [27] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2015), "Technological Competency & Strategic Management: A Review", *Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering, Science and Technology*, Vol. 3, No. 2, September 2015, pp: 21-26
- [28] Singh, CD; and Khamba, JS (2015), "Competency Development through Strategic Management", *International Journal for Multi-Disciplinary Engineering and Business Management*, Volume-3, Issue-3, September 2015, pp: 129-132.
- [29] Singh, CD; Khamba, JS and Kaur H (2015), "Exploring Manufacturing Competency and Strategic Success: A Review", *2nd International Conference on Production & Industrial Engineering 2015 proceedings*, 13 (3) (2015), pp: 1655-1658.
- [30] Singh, CD; Khamba, JS; Singh, R and Singh, N (2014), "Exploring Manufacturing Competencies of a Two Wheeler Manufacturing Unit", *27th International Conference on CAD/CAM, Robotics and Factories of the Future 2014 IOP Publishing IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 65 (2014), pp: 1-9.
- [31] Singh, Rajesh K.; Garg, Suresh K. & Deshmukh, S.G. (2007), "Strategy

- development for competitiveness: a study on Indian auto component sector”, *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol. 56 No. 4, pp. 285-304
- [32] Singh, Rajesh K.; Garg, Suresh K. & Deshmukh, S.G. (2008), “Competency and performance analysis of Indian SMEs and large organizations An exploratory study”, *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 308-32
- [33] Steptoe-Warren, Gail; Howat, Douglas & Hume, Ian (2011), “Strategic thinking and decision making: literature review”, *Journal of Strategy and Management*, Vol. 4 No. 3, pp. 238-250
- [34] Zhi-Yu, W., Yan-Lin, Q. and Shi-He, G. (2006), ‘Quality Competence : a Source of Sustained Competitive Advantage’, *The Journal of China Universities of Posts and Telecommunications*, Vol. 13, Issue No. 1, pp. 104-108